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ERIC

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM

**GENDER
EQUALITY
PLAN**

EMSO ERIC GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

Observing the Ocean to Save the Earth

EMSO ERIC

European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water-column Observatory
European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMSO ERIC)

ERIC established by
the European Commission
Implementing Decision
(EU) 2016/1757

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MESSAGE FROM DIRECTOR GENERAL

Juanjo Dañobeitia, Director General

In the year 2019, EMSO ERIC decided to align its corporate values and strategies with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to fulfill its mission and impact in the society.

The United Nations have introduced Gender Equality as one of the SDGs.

The importance of providing all genders with the means for equal access to education, health care, decent working conditions, and representation in political and economic decision-making processes is of undiscussed benefit for societies at large. As per UN SDG 5, Gender Equality represents a pillar for the economy, making the best use of talents, and it is a “necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world”. Also, the European Commission acknowledges gender planning as an active approach for making real progress towards a more sustainable future.

The gender dimension incorporation into European policies and actions have increasingly speed-up and promoted for adoption within the European organisations. Accordingly, the Consortium is setting the fundamental principles upon which the organisations should operate to eliminate any possible source of discrimination within the Research Infrastructure.

As Director-General of EMSO ERIC, I am glad to introduce the first EMSO Gender Equality Plan as the strategic initiative to define both the context and the process for implementing gender mainstreaming in practice at the workplaces within EMSO Research Infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION

The relative dearth of women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) as well as in research organisations leadership positions is a significant political issue which EMSO ERIC is trying to face, taking the opportunity from implementing its first Gender Equality Plan (GEP). Gender equality requires all genders to access and enjoy the same opportunities. Accordingly, aligned with UN SDG 5, EMSO is strengthening its policies for more inclusive work practices to guarantee that all genders can access the same rewards, resources, and professional growth. EMSO GEP foresees an explicit budget dedicated to gender equality policies, which is needed to promote accountability and transparency in fiscal planning, increase gender-responsiveness in the budget process, and promote gender equality and women's rights.

This document addresses gender issues at all organisational levels, from the governing bodies to the researchers associated with the EMSO ERIC activities in the operative groups. The data reveal considerable variation in female representation across research organisations that are EMSO National Representing Entities, the Central Management Office and Regional Facilities, and fields and roles in scientific activities.

To draw down its GEP, EMSO ERIC sets the following sequential actions:

1. Getting started: Analysis of the political and legislative context
2. Analysing and assessing the state-of-play in the institution: Analysis data collection, procedures, processes and practices assessment and gaps detection in gender equality.
3. Setting up the GEP: Based on the gap analysis, gender-related objectives have been identified and targets set, together with the identification of actions and measures to achieve the goals. Moreover, resources and responsibilities have been defined.
4. Implementing GEP: definition of the activities carried out.
5. Monitoring progress and evaluating GEP: Process and progress assessment and actions adjustment to optimise results

The present document and the specific plan of actions can be updated on yearly basis.

1. GETTING STARTED

REGULATORY BASIS FOR GENDER EQUALITY

Reviewing relevant EU directives in gender equality¹

Current progress in gender equality has arisen from a long historical process, which has been shaped over time by the social transformations and growth of civil awareness in human rights. This paragraph provides a short overview of the EU **gender equality policies** and the relevant European Union legislation, starting from Article 141 EC (former article 119 EEC), which establishes equal pay for women and men; around 15 Directives between 1975 and 2010 testify the importance of this topic in Europe. The Directive on equal pay for men and women (75/117) followed, and together with the Directive on equal treatment of men and women in employment (76/207 as amended by Directive 2002/73), preceded the Directive on equal treatment of men and women in statutory schemes of social security (79/7/EEC) on 19 December 1978. The Principle of equal treatment for men and women in social security matters represents the first requirement: prohibition of direct and indirect sexual discrimination applied to statutory social security schemes. The Principle of equal treatment between men and women was extended later to men and women engaged in an activity

in a self-employed capacity (as amended by Directive 2010/41 / EU, 7 July 2010). Both the Directive on equal treatment of men and women in occupational social security schemes (86/378, as amended by Directive 96/97), and the Directive on equal treatment of men and women engaged in an activity, including agriculture, in a self-employed capacity (86/613), preceded the Directive on equal treatment of men and women in the access to and the supply of goods and services (2004/113). Moreover, in 1992, the Member States adopted a specific directive regarding pregnant workers: the Pregnancy Directive (92/85 / EC), which was followed by the Parental Leave Directive (96/34 and 2010/18 / EU). After 1997 there has been a growing awareness that most part-time workers in the EU are women. So, the legislative focus shifted to the requirement of equal treatment between part-time and full-time workers following the Directive on part-time work (97/81 / EC).

The end of the XX Century marked the time that EU reinforced its competence to take appropriate action and combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, and age or sexual orientation (Article 19 TFEU — (former Article 13 TEC). This phenomenon triggered a movement to adopt national anti-discrimination legislation across Europe, involving the Member States. This movement originated significant changes to the existing legislative framework up to that time, and the In-

stitutions adopted unprecedented new laws and regulations to precisely regulate the prohibition of discrimination, following the requirements of the racial equality directives (2000/43 / EC) and of equality in employment (2000/78 / EC). The latter was not limited to employment and occupation but covered religion or belief, disability, age, and sexual orientation. An effort to synthesize the previous directives was the formulation of the so-called Recast Directive (2006/54), the Principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women engaged in employment and occupation - 5 July 2006. This Directive clarifies and brings together the main provisions regarding direct and indirect sexual discrimination, sexual harassment and harassment in pay (and in access) to work, and occupational social security schemes in a single text. Ensuring the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women represents a central concept of EU gender equality law. It reflects one of the fundamental principles of the European Union: equality between men and women, upheld by the EU gender equality law which is aimed at eliminating inequalities, and promoting equality, between men and women (Articles 2 and 3(3) TEU and 8 TFEU); and combatting discrimination based on sex (Articles 10 and 19 TFEU).

The EU policy for gender equality drove significant legislation in that regard. In addition to the legally binding directives, it provided financial instruments that enabled the implementation of gender equality, financing specific programs, and on instruments of non-binding law which are: the European Pact for Gender Equality; the Strategic Engagement for Gender Equality; and the Gender Equality Strategy. The 2011-2020 European Pact for gender equality was in continuity with the priorities and experiences of the 2010-2015 Strategy for equality between women and

men, which stressed the contribution of gender equality to economic growth and sustainable development. Moreover, in 2015 all Member States of the United Nations adopted the 17 goals of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, in which Gender equality represents a transversal element. It explicitly highlighted the importance of closing gender gaps and supporting gender equality by systematically mainstreaming the gender perspective. The SDG framework includes a specific goal (SDG 5) and a specific indicator on gender budgeting (target 5. C.1.).

We collected the legacy of the European strategic commitment for gender equality 2016-2019. The creation of a dedicated European Commissioner for Equality in 2019 confirmed, once again, that equality represents one of the major priorities of the European Commission. The elements that trace the global priorities draw priority areas for all EU policies and funding programs, and in March 2020, the European Commission published "A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025". It contains a series of EU initiatives and strategies concerning equality, diversity, and inclusion that the Commission is adopting towards "A new push for European democracy". This political priority is reflected in Horizon Europe, where it represents a crosscutting priority: Article 7(6) and Recital 53 of Framework Regulation & Articles 2(2)(e) and 6(3)(e) of the Specific Programme. Moreover, Gender Equality is a renewed European Research Area (ERA) policy priority: Council Conclusions on the New ERA (1 Dec. 2020), and Commission's Communication on A new ERA for Research and Innovation (30 Sept. 2020).

¹ The EU legal framework of reference: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality>. A detailed list of Directives we refer to is reported in the Annex 1 of this document. It has been extracted and modified from the EUROPEAN COMMISSION pub. EU gender equality law – update 2018. Author. Susanne Burri, November 2018. Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers (European Commission), European Network of Legal Experts in the Field of Gender Equality. 18-12 2018 - ISBN978-92-79-95761-1

KEY ITALIAN DIRECTIVES IN GENDER EQUALITY

A focus on the Italian legislation regarding gender equality and gender balance is necessary in consideration that the headquarters of EMSO ERIC are located in Rome.

The significant legal sources related to gender equality and its implementation within the Italian legal system are selected below. The evolution of the Italian legislation on equality and equal employment opportunities starts from the Constitution of the Italian Republic, with articles 3, 37, 48, 51, 117. Indeed, Article 3 of the Italian Constitution guarantees the principle of formal and substantive legal equality. The law 9 February 1963 n. 66, "Admission of women to public offices and professions", confirmed the right of women to access public functions without limitations of duties and career advancement. Direct discrimination regarding access to work was forbidden with the law of 9 December 1977 n. 903: "equal treatment between men and women in the workplace".

This law underlined the constitutional principle of equal pay treatment for the same work of equal value; it also introduced a 'judicial remedy' (Article 15) with an urgent procedure to face discriminatory acts and behaviors against existing or potential employees. Law n. 791/1981: "Provisions on social security" followed. Subsequently, with the law of 10 April 1991 n. 125 "positive actions for the realization of equality between men and women in the world of work" (later amended with Legislative Decree 196/2000), the measures for equal opportunities have been codified for the first time, and the sanctions defined. It was also the first time that indirect discrimination was defined. After the "Declaration and Program of Action adopted at the Fourth UN World Conference on Women", Beijing 1995, the Directive

of the President of the Council of Ministers of March 1997 was issued, "Actions aimed at promoting the attribution of powers and responsibility for women, to recognize and guarantee freedom of choice and social equality for women and men ". Following this action, the concepts of "mainstreaming" emerged in the Italian scenario as a systematic integration of the equal opportunity and gender dimension in policies. The concept of "empowerment" also appeared and was acknowledged as the objective of governmental action to acquire women's power in decision-making processes.

The Charter of Fundamental Rights in 2000, together with other international initiatives, gave further impetus to the evolution of the EU Member States scenarios on gender equality. It was followed by the legislative Decree n. 151/2001 "Consolidated text of the legislative provisions on the protection and support of maternity and paternity", and the amendments to the Constitution of the Italian Republic (l. cost 3/2001), in the new Article 117, with the abrogation of regional laws obstacles and promotion of the full gender equality and equal access to elective offices.

Italy's actions towards gender equality progressed by adopting European Union (EU) directives. The National Code of Equal Opportunities between Women and Men was established by Legislative Decree n. 198 of 2006 and it is considered the Italian legal framework on gender equality and women's empowerment. The Code gathers 11 laws on equal opportunities in a single text, intending to rationalise and harmonise the current legislative provisions on gender equality and promote equal opportunities between women and men in ethical, social, and economic relations and civil political rights. It also introduced the principle of gender mainstreaming, obliging the government to take the gender perspective into account.

STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK AT EMSO ERIC

The European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO) is a distributed research infrastructure consisting of a system of Regional Facilities including fixed seafloor and water column observation platforms and connected facilities. EMSO observation platforms are deployed at key sites around Europe and have long-term, high-resolution, (near)-real-time capabilities to address environmental processes such as climate change, natural hazards and marine ecosystem changes. EMSO European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMSO ERIC), is an intergovernmental organisation hosted by Italy with the function of coordinating and facilitating the operation and the development of state-of-the-art facilities serving a wide range of stakeholders. Countries participating in the consortium include France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, the United Kingdom and Kingdom of Norway.

Considering the nature of the organization, this document intends to cover the gender dimension of those activities and aspects strictly associated with the European Research Consortium. Therefore, the focus of the analysis on the gender dimension as well as the actions planned in this current Gender Equality Plan will be addressed to:

GOVERNING BODIES:

- Assembly of Members (AoM)
- Executive Committee (ExCom)
- Director General (DG)
- Advisory Committee (AC)

OPERATIVE GROUPS:

- Service groups

The Central Management Office (CMO) will be considered as part of the DG Governing Body for the purpose of this document, since it is the office established with the aim of assisting the Director General in performing his functions.

EMSO ERIC's commitment towards diversity and inclusion is a process that started in the early stage of the organization's setup. In 2017 the ERIC kicked off its process towards promoting and adopting a policy on diversity and inclusion through its first gender analysis, finalised to outline the EMSO ERIC Gender Equality strategy. In this occasion, the Consortium established the following key principles:

EMPLOYMENT AND COMPENSATION

- 1) To ensure fair and comparable wages, hours, and benefits for comparable work.
- 2) To undertake verifiable actions to recruit women candidates and retain women employees from underrepresented group and for non-traditional positions.
- 3) To prohibit discrimination based on marital, parental or reproductive status in all employment or promotion decision.
- 4) To allow for interruptions in work for maternity leave, parental, leave, and family-related responsibilities.
- 5) To recognize that the economic and physical vulnerability of pregnant workers and pregnant life partners makes it necessary for them to be granted the right to maternity benefits. Maternity benefits for EMSO ERIC employees are subject to the Italian law (Dlgs n. 151/2001).
- 6) To implement equitable policies for non-salaried employees conducting temporary and/or temporary work.

- 7) To ensure equitable layoffs that do not disproportionately affect women.

HEALTH, SAFETY AND FREEDOM FROM VIOLENCE

- 1) To prohibit and prevent all forms of violence and harassment in the workplace, including verbal, physical.
- 2) To provide and promote policies and programs addressing domestic violence.
- 3) To disclose and eliminate unsafe working conditions in the workplace, particularly in cases of suspected adverse effects on the health of women, including reproductive health.

WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT

- 1) To implement a variety of flexible work options, including workforce exit and re-entry opportunities, and support women returning to positions of equal pay and status.
- 2) To promote the use of family leave, dependent care, and wellness programs, allowing time-off from work for employees seeking medical care or treatment, including family planning and reproductive health care.
- 3) To support access to childcare by providing referrals to childcare services.
- 4) To provide equal opportunities for women and access to education, including literacy, vocational, and information technology training.
- 5) To provide professional development opportunities that include formal or informal

2 Key principle identified on the basis of 2017 analysis.

networking, client development activities, and mentoring programs at all levels.

MANAGEMENT AND GOVERNANCE

- 1) To undertake proactive efforts to recruit and appoint women to managerial positions².
- 2) To undertake proactive efforts to assure participation by women in decision-making and governance at all levels and in all areas of the business, including budgetary decision-making.
- 3) To include gender equality improvement as a factor in performance measures and provide resources to support gender initiatives.

BUSINESS, SUPPLY CHAIN AND MARKETING PRACTICES

- 1) To maintain ethical marketing standards by respecting the dignity of women in all sales, promotional, and advertising materials, and to eliminate any form of gender or sexual exploitation in marketing and advertising campaigns.
- 2) To encourage and support women's entrepreneurship seeking business relationships with women-owned businesses and vendors, including micro-enterprises, and work with them to arrange fair credit and lending terms.
- 3) To ensure that these principles are observed not only with respect to employees, but also business partners such as independent contractors, sub-contractors, home-based workers, vendors, and suppliers.
- 4) To take these principles into consideration in product and service development

and major business decisions, such as mergers, acquisitions, joint venture partnerships, and financing.

CIVIC AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

- 1) To encourage philanthropic foundations promoting equal opportunities through programmatic initiatives and investments.
- 2) To encourage women and girls to enter non-traditional fields by providing accessible career information and training programs designed specifically for them.
- 3) To respect freedom of association among all employees.
- 4) To deprecate situations where cultural differences or customs are used to deny the basic human rights of women and girls.

LEADERSHIP, TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY

- 1) To commit to gender equality through a DG statement or comparably prominent means and prominently display the commitment in the workplace and/or make it available to all employees in a readily accessible form.
- 2) To establish benchmarks to measure and monitor progress toward gender equality and to report the results publicly.
- 3) To implement company policies, training, and internal reporting processes to ensure implementation of gender equality throughout the organization and to conduct periodic self-evaluations through data collection and analysis, audits, public disclosure, and reporting.
- 4) To establish a clear, unbiased, non-retal-

atory grievance policy allowing employees to comment or complain about their treatment in the workplace.

- 5) To engage in constructive dialogue with stakeholder groups, including employees, non-governmental organizations, business associations, investors, customers, and the media on progress in implementing the organization's commitment to gender equality.
- 6) To be transparent in the implementation of these commitments and promote endorsement and implementation by affiliates, vendors, suppliers, customers, and others with whom the organization does business.
- 7) To ensure that government relations and corporate political spending policies and practices incorporate the commitment to gender equality.

balance. This harmonization simplifies the collaboration between EMSO ERIC and EMSO National Representing Entities in terms of Gender Policy and Gender actions.

RELATION WITH GEPS OF EMSO NATIONAL REPRESENTING ENTITIES

At the time of drafting the GEP, many of EMSO National Representing Entities already had adopted a Gender Equality Plan while others were still in the phase of finalization of the document. The existing GEPS are very different from each other; in fact, there are documents that cover a wider period (for example 2017-2022, University of Bergen) and others that have not set a long-term perspective; some of them have already established their Gender policy, in particular the academic institutions, whereas others are currently setting up the strategy.

Remarkably, having the European Commission provided some precise guidelines, most of the Gender Equality Plans available are already harmonised in their main parts, such as the areas of the measures to apply for ensuring the gender

2. ANALYSING AND ASSESSING THE STATE-OF-PLAY IN EMSO ERIC

A first phase of analysis aimed at collecting data, assessing procedures, processes and practices and detecting gaps in gender equality has been carried out. This phase represents the essential preparatory activity for planning Gender Equality and provides the necessary information to integrate a gender perspective into EMSO ERIC policies, programs, and projects.

The analysis phase started in 2017 during the implementation phase of the organization and ended in late 2021 with a final update of the data.

GENDER REPRESENTATION IN EMSO ERIC, IMPLEMENTATION PHASE

EMSO carried out the first gender study in 2017. The study assessed differences in conditions, participation rates, decision making power and needs. The work was coordinated by the Central Management Office in the research infrastructure framework implementation project, EMSO-Link (H2020-EU funded project n. 731036), to identify gaps among the Research Institutions, beneficiaries of the project, and EMSO Regional Facility Leaders (i.e., representatives) at the same time.

EMSO identified gaps between women and men regarding their respective position and the distribution of resources, opportunities, constraints and power within the Research Infrastructure.

Afterward, the investigation was carried out to facilitate the definition of future EMSO objectives and interventions to address gender inequalities and meet the organisational needs of integrating a gender perspective into policies, programs and projects. This first analysis was based on a survey circulated among the EMSO-Link partners to obtain baseline data on the gender distribution in their respective organisations. The gender analysis identified the differences between women and men in terms of their relative position in the EMSO community and the distribution of resources, opportunities and power in EMSO Regional Facilities has been the starting point. In this way, the gender analysis produced the fundamental information needed to develop interventions for addressing gender inequalities and for meeting the different needs of women and men.

The key steps of the process of producing a gender dataset included:

- the selection of topics that needed to be investigated;
- the identification of the data needed to understand gender differentials and roles of women and men in the different positions (both in EMSO-Link project and in the Partner organisations);
- the development of methods of analysis that reflected the diversity of women and men in the organisations;

- the development of tools for data collection and survey design, such as the definition of sample type and questionnaire development;
- the collection and processing of data using Google Forms to deliver reliable results in real-time,
- the analysis and presentation of responses in easy-to-use formats.

The development of table shells (templates of tables to be produced) and multivariate models before developing a questionnaire, showed some difficulties at an early stage. The incorporation of a gender perspective into questionnaire design involved consideration of a number of factors included:

- the data items required to meet the objectives of the collection;
- the concepts and definitions associated with these data items;
- the conversion of these data items into questions.

The questionnaire used in the initial survey was submitted to each project partner with the aim of assessing the gender situation in these organisations and in the project in order to help us in structuring the EMSO ERIC Gender Equality Strategy. It was composed of the following questions:

Q1. WHO YOU ARE

NAME AND SURNAME/PARTNER

Q2. NUMBER OF PERSONS WORKING ON EMSO-LINK

Q3. ROLE IN THE ORGANISATION F/M:

- Senior Manager
- Junior Manager
- Senior Administrative
- Junior Administrative
- Researcher Director

- Senior Researcher
- Junior Researcher
- Senior Technical
- Junior Technical
- Other

Q4. ROLE IN THE PROJECT:

- WP Leader
- Task Leader
- Team member

Q5. YOUR ORGANISATION HAS A GENDER EQUALITY STRATEGY

Q6. GENDER PARITY IN STAFF HAS BEEN ACHIEVED IN YOUR ORGANISATIONAL AREA

Q7. GENDER BALANCE IS INCLUDED IN THE RECRUITMENT POLICY IN YOUR ORGANISATIONAL AREA

The analysis focused on three types of data: 'population censuses' (Female or Male); 'role surveys'; and 'gender equality strategy' records for each institution.

Role in the organisation represents a critical issue. Equality in decision-making is essential to women's empowerment, and women's equal participation in decision-making is a demand for justice or democracy and a necessary condition for women's interests to be considered.

In the following paragraph, we report the results from the first exercise done in the frame of the implementation project of the Research Infrastructure. The coordination team (EMSO-link) sent the questionnaire to 11 research institutions, project partners and Representing Entities within the Consortium. The questionnaire was also extended to the EMSO ERIC governance, central management, and community to include all the levels of the community in the Gender Equality Strategy. A quantitative data set is presented below in the form of charts and diagrams. By contrast, qualitative data (data that records the three last answers: Q5, Q6 and Q7) are discussed in ordinary prose.

ANALYSING DATA

A | General description and digitization of the EMSO ERIC Implementation Project

The first overall impression of the data set can be observed in the two pie charts in Figure 1. The left pie chart in Figure 1 illustrates the relative proportion of men and women involved in the EMSO implementation project. As a first evidence, the percentage of males (65,9%) is about two thirds than the percentage of females (34,1%). The pie chart on the right gives a breakdown of the 34.1% of females in terms of distribution across the different project partners: INGV has the highest proportion of females involved in EMSO-Link (14,8%), followed by GEOECOMAR, NERC and IFREMER with just a three per cent difference (around 11% each). The figure for all the other Partners is 7.4%.

Figure 1
Females and males in EMSO-Link (left pie chart); females' distribution by partners (right pie chart)

Moreover, we integrated data representation by using bar charts, which allow for easy comparisons between data sets: the length of bars shows differences between categories. In order to understand the behavior in the individual organisations, we examined data comparing the percentage of males and females from each organisation involved in EMSO-Link.

Figure 2 shows that the proportion of women involved in the project varies depending on partners. There are three partners where women presence is higher than men (more than 50%): EMSO ERIC, INGV and GEOECOMAR. There are evident disparities in the commitment to gender equality if we compare these three organisations with UPC, IFREMER, HCMR, CNRS (roughly 66% of males) and with IPMA, the partner with the highest male percentage (81.8%).

Figure 2.
Percentage of males (blue) and females (red) involved in the EMSO LINK project

One of the primary purposes of the first analysis was to evaluate equal opportunities for women in leadership positions within the project (see Figure 3). In this regard, our findings essentially confirmed that the proportion of WP Leader positions in INGV and CNRS is slightly higher than other Partners. However, the general trend shows that women are less likely to be recruited or promoted to leadership positions. As demonstrated by the data presented in earlier sections, women are less likely to be in senior positions.

B | The role of the people within the re-search institutions partners of the EMSO ERIC implementation project (EMSO LINK)

Here we briefly analysed the people involved in the EMSO ERIC implementation project within their organisations. The results suggest that males involved in the project have a higher role in the organisation than the females. In contrast, females are more involved in administrative tasks or cover Junior positions. In particular, 35 out of

Figure 3.
Gender distribution of WP Leadership

52 Directors or Senior roles are covered by males, while females cover 11 out of 17 Junior roles. The percentage distribution of males and females and the position in the organization is shown in Figure 4. Data show that females involved in the project were usually under the supervision of males, which cover a higher role in the organizations.

Figure 4.
Percentage of gender distribution with respect to the positions in the organization

C | Gender in partners' organizations

The last set of questions (Q5, Q6 and Q7) refers to the gender dimension in the organisations partners of the EMSO ERIC implementation project. The answers helped us to assess if any gender strategy was already available from the partners and understand how the gender balance was perceived. The last two questions (Gender parity in staff has been achieved in the interviewee's organizational area; Gender balance is included in the recruitment policy in the interviewee's organizational area) relies in some cases on personal perception rather than on objective data. We read these results as a lack of internal communication within these organizations about the gender policies that are applied in the recruitment policy. Those people who gave a positive answer when they were asked about the availability of a gender strategy within their organization, on the contrary, gave coherent answers to the other questions, declaring that the gender parity has been achieved or that the recruitment policy includes the gender balance.

GENDER REPRESENTATION IN EMSO ERIC STATE-OF-PLAY

EMSO ERIC Gender Equality Strategy was established in 2017, in the framework of the implementing project EMSO LINK. In 2021, EMSO ERIC worked on the publication of the specific implementing document "Gender Equality Plan", which will fix concrete measures and actions for carrying out such a strategy in the following two years. An essential step for the definition of these measures has been the analysis of gender representation data which started with a first data study in 2017 and which was finalised with a second round of data collection at the end of 2021.

This second data analysis has been based on a specific e-survey (Google Form) elaborated in October 2021 and submitted in November 2021, with the possibility to collect responses until the first half of December 2021.

The selection of the target audience was discussed in depth and examined in order to track the most relevant data from people involved in EMSO ERIC activities at all levels of engagement/participation. The questionnaire was offered to people involved in the EMSO ERIC activities according to a legal framework, such as the permanent and temporary staff employed by the organization, and also to people formally involved in the general management and in the main decision-making processes of the organization (e.g., Assembly of Members, service groups and advisory committee members).

More specifically, the e-survey was addressed to:

- **Director General and Central Management Office members**
- **Assembly of Members representatives**
- **Executive Committee members**
- **Advisory Committee members**
- **Service Groups members**
- **Regional Team Leaders**

for a total of 103 people. It was possible to collect 50 responses defining a good representative sample for the data analysis.

The survey was designed with the objective to update and analyse objective data while the study of subjective data (e.g., gender balance perceptions) was postponed to after the configuration of a formal gender balance framework. The data were collected according to four main sections:

1. General Information includes male/female question
2. Role in the organization represents the

position of the interviewee in its organization of origin.

3. Involvement in EMSO ERIC organization includes the questions aimed at tracking the composition of the different EMSO ERIC operative groups and decision-making bodies.
4. Position in EMSO ERIC organization represents the information related to the level of responsibility taken by the interviewee in the execution of the EMSO ERIC activities.

Analysing Data

Overview from the EMSO ERIC Community

The first overview of the gender balance dataset is illustrated in Figure 5.

Data show the relative proportion of men and women involved in the EMSO ERIC activities: there are 52% of males, 46% of females and 2% unspecified data.

Figure 5. Gender distribution representation in EMSO ERIC activities

A breakdown in terms of their distribution among the different bodies and operative groups of EMSO ERIC are displayed in Figure 6, where

the proportion of women involved in all the governing bodies is less than 40%, while in the Service Groups the percentage exceeds the 50%, reaching a percentage of 62%. The histogram shows a significant variation on the gender balance between Governing Bodies and operative groups such as the Service Groups. It shows that in the Service Groups there is the highest proportion of women, while in all the Governing Bodies (DG, AoM, ExCom, AC) there is a higher proportion of men. Among the Governing Bodies, the Assembly of Members shows the lowest percentage of females with just 25% while the Central Management office shows the highest percentage with 38%.

Figure 6. Gender distribution in EMSO ERIC activities detailed for Governing Bodies and Operative groups

A | The leadership positions in EMSO ERIC

For assessing the gender balance in the EMSO ERIC leadership positions, an explicit request was made to reply to a question regarding the interviewee's position in the Governing Body or Service Group to which they belong.

The results confirm the gender imbalance in the Governing Bodies, showing a higher proportion of men acting in leadership positions (Figure 7). In detail, 13 leadership positions were recorded

among the interviewees, of which 9 are men, 3 women and 1 unspecified.

LEADERSHIP POSITIONS IN EMSO ERIC ACTIVITES

Figure 7. Gender distribution of leadership positions in EMSO ERIC activities

B | The role of the people within the research institutions

Figure 8 illustrates the roles that people involved in EMSO ERIC's activities carry out within their institutions. The results displays that the men have a slightly higher ranking role in their institutions than women, while women are more involved in administrative tasks or technical activities: 52,5% of Directors or Senior roles are covered by men, while women cover 47,5%.

ROLES IN THE INSTITUTIONS

Figure 8. Gender representation of the different roles at institutions level

TRENDS

In this section we compare the two data collections, gathered in 2017 and in 2021 respectively, which differ slightly in the sampling strategy; in 2017 the sample was taken by participation in the EMSO LINK project while in 2021 the sample was taken directly from the activities of EMSO ERIC. Importantly, the two data collection can be considered comparable and relevant since the population in the two surveys is almost the same while the institutional framework changed, due to the evolving status of the organization.

- After comparing the proportion of men and women involved in EMSO implementation phase in 2017 and the proportion of men and women involved in EMSO ERIC activities in 2021, we noticed a positive trend in terms of women participation (Figure 9).

The men involved in 2017 were 65,9% while in 2021 they were about 52%; the women engaged in EMSO in 2017 were about 34% while in 2021 they were 46%.

INVOLVEMENT IN EMSO ACTIVITIES: GENERAL TREND

Figure 9. Gender distribution evolution from 2017 to 2021 at the EMSO ERIC.

- Conversely, data on leadership positions collected in 2017 and those collected in 2021 are not easily comparable because in the first case data referred to people acting as Work

Package Leader within a funded project, while in 2021 the leadership positions are related to the internal organization of the EMSO ERIC. Nevertheless, it's crucial to have a clear understanding on the trend of the gender representations in roles that are crucial for decision-making processes.

LEADERSHIP POSITIONS IN EMSO ACTIVITIES

Figure 10.
Gender distribution evolution from 2017 to 2021 for the leadership positions at EMSO ERIC

Figure 10 shows a significant negative trend in the participation of women in leadership positions.

3. SETTING UP THE EMSO ERIC GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

The EMSO ERIC Gender Equality Plan (EE GEP) has been developed around the EIGE's gender mainstreaming cycle, the methodology proposed by the European Institute for Gender Equality, where each phase corresponds to a step to develop the Plan. The EE GEP can be updated on yearly basis, according to the EMSO ERIC overall strategy to ensure the most current practices in the gender equality issues align with the organisation's needs.

The EE GEP included:

1. An analysis of the political and legislative context.
2. An analysis phase to collect data, assess procedures, processes and practices and detect gaps in gender equality.
3. Planning phase- Based on the gap analysis, identify gender-related objectives, set targets, actions and measures to achieve the goals. Moreover, resources and responsibilities are defined with an agreed timeline.
4. Implementation of the activities.
5. Monitoring phase - assessing processes and progress and adjusting actions, undertaking measures to optimize results.

EE GEP is a public document, with a specific plan of actions.

It is an institutional official document signed by the Director-General and submitted to the Assembly of Members for approval. It is going to be disseminated within the EMSO-related institutions and community. It is useful to reaffirm that EE GEP is based on specific data on gender of staff across roles and leadership within EMSO ERIC governance, central office, and research institutions operating for the EE activities.

Periodical Data collections and monitoring are planned across all staff categories, and results shall be collated into specific reports. They will inform the management about the ongoing evaluation of progress. The report structure is designed for the dissemination of the EMSO ERIC commitment to gender equality fulfillment. It highlights goals, actions and includes dedicated resources to design, implement, and monitoring the process. Moreover, EMSO ERIC will undertake actions to develop gender competence and tackle gender bias among staff, leaders, and decision-makers. Training, workshops, and communication activities are the main actions identified to raise awareness on this issue.

SPECIFIC PLAN OF ACTIONS

EMSO ERIC is willing to reduce the underrepresentation of women in its governing bodies and operative groups significantly. The organisation sets the fundamental principles on which it should operate to prevent any possible source of discrimination. The main goal is to address potential structural inequalities within its organisation by advocating for a change in the associated research organisations.

The conclusions of the above analysis allowed EMSO to identify the main areas of intervention (Gender Dimensions) to be addressed in the Gender Equality Plan. The organisation identified gender-related objectives, set targets, and actions to achieve the goals based on the gap analysis.

The five Gender Dimensions identified are:

1. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
2. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression and promotion of the condition of access to personal development;
3. Work-life balance ;
4. Integration of the gender dimension into EMSO ERIC organizational culture;
5. Gender-based violence including sexual harassment, sexist attitudes and perception of discrimination.

GENDER BUDGETING

To achieve the objectives of the GEP and ensure sustainability, EMSO ERIC will allocate economic resources in terms of human resources to the implementation of the GEP. As for human resources, EMSO ERIC will deploy resources corresponding to 2 person/months in each fiscal year, initially for 2022 and 2023. This amount can be reviewed annually based of new GEP needs communicated by the CMO Programme manager. The procedures for assigning staff will consider the skills necessary for carrying out the activities envisaged by this GEP document. When necessary, EMSO ERIC will cover additional investments for training and coaching activities.

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	TARGET	INDICATORS	PERSON IN CHARGE	TIME SCHEDULING FOR MONITORING
1. GENDER BALANCE IN LEADERSHIP AND DECISION-MAKING					
To reach gender equality in decision-making and programmatic bodies	Promote gender balance in the decision-making bodies	Delegates of Members States in Assembly of Members, members of Executive Committee	Number of men and women in AoM and in ExCom	DG	yearly
	Endorse gender equality in decision-making roles and organizational positions	DG, Heads of Regional Teams, Service Groups Leaders, CMO officers	Number of men and women as Heads of Regional Teams, Service Groups Leaders, CMO officers	DG	yearly
	Promote gender balance in accessing selections to higher education courses and trainings	CMO officers	Number of men and women accessing higher education courses and trainings	Policy officer	yearly
2. GENDER EQUALITY IN RECRUITMENT AND CAREER PROGRESSION AND PROMOTION OF THE CONDITION OF ACCESS TO PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT					
Assurance gender equality in EMSO ERIC Recruitment policy and career progression	Endorse gender equality dimension in EMSO ERIC recruitment procedures	DG and recruitment committees	Number of men and women in recruitment committees	DG	yearly
3. WORK-LIFE BALANCE					
Improvement of work-life balance through the reconciliation of private life and work times	Promoting Smart working and other flexible working time arrangements, also on personalised basis	All staff	number of measures	DG	yearly
	Dissemination (in EE communication channels) of measures adopted by EE and its national representing entities regarding work-life balance		number of articles/posts	Policy officer supported by communication officer	yearly

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	TARGET	INDICATORS	PERSON IN CHARGE	TIME SCHEDULING FOR MONITORING
4. INTEGRATION OF GENDER DIMENSION INTO EMSO ERIC ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE					
Improve gender equality in research activities	Promote gender balance in research projects where EMSO ERIC participates	All staff	number of men and women working in the projects	DG	yearly
Improve gender equality in external activities	Promote gender balance in conferences, dissemination events, workshops etc.	All staff	number of men and women invited as speakers in external events	Policy officer supported by communication officer	yearly
5. GENDER- BASED VIOLENCE INCLUDING SEXUAL HARASSMENT, SEXIST ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTION OF DISCRIMINATION					
Dissemination campaign on the topic of gender equality	Quarterly publication of articles / posts with a focus on women in science (from EMSO ERIC and/ or its facilities), in the EMSO ERIC institutional communication channels (e.g., newsletters and social channels)	All staff and national representing entities of EMSO ERIC	number of articles/ posts	Policy officer supported by communication officer	yearly
Improvement of work-life balance through the reconciliation of private life and work times	Promoting Smart working and other flexible working time arrangements, also on personalised basis	All staff	number of measures	DG	yearly
	Organization of at least 1 training/ information meetings on gender equality issues with experts (internal/external)	All staff and EE community	number of trainings/ meetings organized	Policy officer	
	Dissemination of reports, statistics and internal monitoring results prepared by policy officer in charge for gender dimension	All EE staff and EE communities [EE national representing entities]	number of dissemination activities on such data	Policy officer supported by communication officer	yearly
	Control of compliance with gender language in communication and strategic documents of the ERIC	All staff	number of non-compliance	Policy officer and communication officer	yearly
	Dissemination of supporting services in case of need (e.g., National equality councilor)	All staff and EE community	number dissemination activities on activity	Policy officer supported by communication officer	

NEXT STEPS

This report represents a baseline for any further developments.

On yearly basis, EMSO ERIC can revise the current document on the basis of monitoring outcomes. Improvements can be accomplished with a more targeted definition of the sample and inclusion of interviewees' perceptions.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Anita Di Chiara, research granter at INGV (Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia), for her useful comments and general revision.

Annex 1- Directives

- Council Directive 75/117/EEC of 10 February 1975 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the application of the Principle of equal pay for men and women OJ L 45, 19.2.1975, pp. 19–20.
- Council Directive 76/207/EEC of 9 February 1976 on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions, OJ 1976, L 39/40 (repealed).
- Council Directive 79/7/EEC of 19 December 1978 on the progressive implementation of the Principle of equal treatment for men and women in matters of social security OJ L 6, 10.1.1979, pp. 24–25.
- Council Directive 86/378/EEC of 24 July 1986 on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in occupational social security schemes, OJ 1986, L 225/40 (repealed).
- Council Directive 86/613/EEC of 11 December 1986 on the application of the Principle of equal treatment between men and women engaged in an activity, including agriculture, in a self-employed capacity, and on the protection of self-employed women during pregnancy and motherhood OJ L 359, 19.12.1986, pp. 56–58.
- Council Directive 92/85/EEC of 19 October 1992 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding (tenth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC) OJ L 348, 28.11.1992, pp. 1–8.
- Council Directive 96/34/EC of 3 June 1996 on the framework agreement on parental leave concluded by UNICE, CEEP and the ETUC OJ L 145, 19.6.1996, pp. 4–9.
- Council Directive 96/97/EC of 20 December 1996 amending Directive 86/378/EEC on the implementation of the Principle of equal treatment for men and women in occupational social security schemes OJ L 46, 17.2.1997, pp. 20–24.
- Council Directive 97/80/EC of 15 December 1997 on the burden of proof in cases of discrimination based on sex, OJ 1998, L 14/6 (repealed).
- Council Directive 97/81/EC of 15 December 1997 concerning the Framework Agreement on part-time work concluded by UNICE, CEEP and the ETUC, OJ 1998, L 14/9.
- Directive 2002/73/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 September 2002 amending Council Directive 76/207/EEC on the implementation of the Principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions OJ L 269, 5.10.2002, pp. 15–20.
- Council Directive 2004/113/EC of 13 December 2004 implementing the Principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services OJ L 373, 21.12.2004, pp. 37–43.

- Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the Principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast) OJ L 204, 26.7.2006, pp. 23-36.
- Council Directive 2010/18/EU of 8 March 2010 implementing the revised Framework Agreement on parental leave concluded by BUSINESSEUROPE, UEAPME, CEEP and ETUC and repealing Directive 96/34/EC (Text with EEA relevance), pp 276-283
- Directive 2010/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 July 2010 on the application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women engaged in an activity in a self-employed capacity and repealing Council Directive 86/613/EEC, pp 245-250

Annex 2- Documents and links

- **EU Gender Equality Strategy (2020-2025)**
- **European Pact for Gender Equality (2011-2020)**
- **Europe 2020 - A European strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth**
- **Strategic Engagement for Gender Equality (2016-2019)**
- **Strategy for Equality between men and women (2010-2015)**
- **Annual reports on Equality between women and men (European Commission)**
- **Special Eurobarometer 428 on Gender Equality**

Annex 3 Data Analysis 2017

WP LEADER IN EMSO ERIC

- EMSO ERIC
- IFREMER
- GEOECOMAR
- HCMR
- UPC
- CNRS
- Marine Institute
- INGV
- INNOVA
- IPMA
- NERC

WP LEADERS IN EMSO ERIC			
	MALES	FEMALES	TOT
EMSO ERIC			
WP Leader	1	1	2
HCMR			
WP Leader	1	0	1
Marine Institute			
WP Leader	1	0	1
IPMA			
WP Leader	0	0	0
IFREMER			
WP Leader	1	0	1
UPC			
WP Leader	0	0	0
INGV			
WP Leader	0	1	1
NERC			
WP Leader	1	0	1
GEOECOMAR			
WP Leader	0	0	0
CNRS			
WP Leader	0	1	1
INNOVA			
WP Leader	0	0	0
TOTAL	5	3	8

TEAM MEMBERS IN EMSO-LINK

TEAM MEMBERS IN EMSO-LINK			
	MALES	FEMALES	TOT
EMSO ERIC			
Team member	0	1	1
HCMR			
Team member	4	2	6
Marine Institute			
Team member	0	0	0
IPMA			
Team member	6	2	8
IFREMER			
Team member	4	2	6
UPC			
Team member	3	2	5
INGV			
Team member	2	3	5
NERC			
Team member	2	2	4
GEOECOMAR			
Team member	1	3	4
CNRS			
Team member	6	1	7
INNOVA			
Team member	1	1	2
TOTAL	29	19	48

PARTNERS | gender equality strategy D1.3

ROLE IN THE ORGANISATION

EMSO ERIC	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
FEMALES	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
% MALES		0,5	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% FEMALES		0,5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
HCMR	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
% MALES	1	-	-	-	-	1	0	1	0	-
% FEMALES	0	-	-	-	-	0	1	0	1	-
Marine Institute	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
FEMALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
% MALES		0	1	-	-	1	-	0	-	-
% FEMALES	1	0	-	-	0	-	1	-	-	-
IPMA	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	2	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
% MALES		-	-	-	-	-	0,75	-	1	-
% FEMALES	-	-	-	-	-	0,25	-	0	-	-
IFREMER	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	0
FEMALES	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
% MALES	1	-	0,5	-	-	-	-	0,6	1	-
% FEMALES	0	-	0,5	-	-	-	-	0,4	0	-
UPC	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
% MALES		0,5	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
% FEMALES		0,5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

INGV	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
FEMALES	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0
% MALES	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0,5	1	-
% FEMALES	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	0,5	0	-
NERC	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
FEMALES	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
% MALES	1	0	-	0	-	0,5	1	-	0,5	-
% FEMALES	0	1	-	1	-	0,5	0	-	0,5	-
GEOECOMAR	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
% MALES	-	-	-	0	-	-	1	-	-	0
% FEMALES	-	-	1	-	-	0	-	-	1	-
CNRS	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	2	0	0
FEMALES	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
% MALES	-	-	0	-	-	-	0,8	-	1	-
% FEMALES	-	1	-	-	-	0,2	-	0	-	-
INNOVA	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
FEMALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
% MALES	0,5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,5	-
% FEMALES	0,5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,5	-
MALES	6	1	1	0	1	14	1	13	4	0
FEMALES	3	3	4	1	1	5	3	4	4	0
% MALES	0,67	0,25	0,20	0,00	0,50	0,74	0,25	0,76	0,50	-
% FEMALES	0,33	0,75	0,80	1,00	0,50	0,26	0,75	0,24	0,50	0,50
TOTAL	9	4	5	1	2	19	4	17	8	0

PARTNERS | gender equality strategy D1.3

ROLE IN THE ORGANISATION

EMSO ERIC	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
FEMALES	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HCMR	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
Marine Institute	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
FEMALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
IPMA	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	2	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
IFREMER	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	0
FEMALES	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
UPC	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
INGV	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
FEMALES	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0
NERC	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
FEMALES	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
GEOECOMAR	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
FEMALES	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
CNRS	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	2	0	0
FEMALES	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
INNOVA	M S	M J	AS	AJ	RD	RS	RJ	TS	TJ	OTHER
MALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
FEMALES	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0

PARTNERS | ROLE IN THE ORGANISATION

ROLE	% FEMALE
Senior Manager	33
Junior Manager	75
Senior Administrative	80
Junior Administrative	100
Researcher Director	50
Senior Researcher	26
Junior Researcher	75
Senior Technical	24
Junior Technical	50
Other	-

ROLE	% MALE
Senior Manager	67
Junior Manager	25
Senior Administrative	20
Junior Administrative	0
Researcher Director	50
Senior Researcher	74
Junior Researcher	25
Senior Technical	76
Junior Technical	50
Other	

EMSO LINK | gender equality strategy D1.3

PEOPLE WORKING ON EMSO-LINK

EMSO ERIC	MALE	FEMALE
Paola Materia	1	2
Total	1	2
HCMR		
Sylvia Christodoulaki	5	2
Total	5	2
Marine Institute		
Deirdre Fitzhenry	2	2
Total	2	2
IPMA		
Julio Guerra	9	2
Total	9	2
IFREMER		
Jérôme Blandin	6	3
Total	6	3
UPC		
Joaquin Del Rio	4	2
Total	4	2
INGV		
Laura Beranzoli	2	4
Total	2	4
NERC		
Henry Ruhl	4	3
Total	4	3
GEOECOMAR		
Daniela Vasile	1	3
Total	1	3
CNRS		
Déborah Chavrit	6	2
Total	6	2
INNOVA		
Antonella Vulcano	2	2
Total	2	2
TOTAL	29	15

● MALES ● FEMALES

EMSO LINK | gender equality strategy D1.3

PEOPLE WORKING ON EMSO-LINK

EMSO ERIC	MALE	FEMALE	% MALE	% FEMALE
Paola Materia	1	2		
Total	1	2	33,3	66,7
HCMR				
Sylvia Christodoulaki	5	2		
Total	5	2	71,4	28,6
Marine Institute				
Deirdre Fitzhenry	2	2		
Total	2	2	50,0	50,0
IPMA				
Julio Guerra	9	2		
Total	9	2	81,8	18,2
IFREMER				
Jérôme Blandin	6	3		
Total	6	3	66,7	33,3
UPC				
Joaquin Del Rio	4	2		
Total	4	2	66,7	33,3
INGV				
Laura Beranzoli	2	4		
Total	2	4	33,3	66,7
NERC				
Henry Ruhl	4	3		
Total	4	3	57,1	42,9
GEOECOMAR				
Daniela Vasile	1	3		
Total	1	3	25,0	75,0
CNRS				
Déborah Chavrit	6	2		
Total	6	2	75,0	25,0
INNOVA				
Antonella Vulcano	2	2		
Total	2	2	50,0	50,0
TOTAL	29	15	65,9	34,1

100,0

80,0

60,0

40,0

20,0

0,0

EMSD ERIC

HCMR

Marine Institute

IPMA

IFREMER

UPC

INGY

NERC

GEDECOMAR

CNRS

INNOVA

WP LEADER IN EMSO-LINK

WP LEADERS IN EMSO-LINK

	MALES	FEMALES	TOT
EMSO ERIC			
WP Leader	1	1	2
HCMR			
WP Leader	1	0	1
Marine Institute			
WP Leader	1	0	1
IPMA			
WP Leader	0	0	0
IFREMER			
WP Leader	1	0	1
UPC			
WP Leader	0	0	0
INGV			
WP Leader	0	1	1
NERC			
WP Leader	1	0	1
GEOECOMAR			
WP Leader	0	0	0
CNRS			
WP Leader	0	1	1
INNOVA			
WP Leader	0	0	0
TOTAL	5	3	8

TEAM MEMEBRS IN EMSO-LINK

TEAM MEMBERS IN EMSO-LINK

	MALES	FEMALES	TOT
EMSO ERIC			
Team member	0	1	1
HCNR			
Team member	4	2	6
Marine Institute			
Team member	0	0	0
IPMA			
Team member	6	2	8
IFREMER			
Team member	4	2	6
UPC			
Team member	3	2	5
INGV			
Team member	2	3	5
NERC			
Team member	2	2	4
GEOCOMAR			
Team member	1	3	4
CNRS			
Team member	6	1	7
INNOVA			
Team member	1	1	2
TOTAL	29	19	48

Annex 4 - Data Analysis 2021

GENDER DISTRIBUTION IN EMSO ERIC ACTIVITIES: involvement in governing bodies VS involvement in service groups				
	MALE	FEMALE	NA	TOT
Involved in Governing Bodies	18	10	1	29
Involved in Service Groups	8	13	0	21

Table 2

GENDER DISTRIBUTION IN EMSO ERIC ACTIVITIES detailed for Governing Bodies and Operative groups				
	MALE	FEMALE	NA	TOT
DG+CMO	5	3		8
Assembly of Members	3	1		4
Executive Committee	7	4	1	12
Advisory Committee	3	2		5
Service Group members	8	13		21

Table 3

GENDER DISTRIBUTION IN EMSO ERIC ACTIVITIES

Chart 1: Gender distribution representation in EMSO ERIC activities

INVOLVEMENT IN EMSO ERIC ACTIVITIES (organization level)

Chart 2: Gender distribution in EMSO ERIC activities detailed for Governing Bodies and Operative groups

GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF LEADERSHIP POSITIONS IN EMSO ERIC ACTIVITIES				
	MALE	FEMALE	NA	TOT
Leadership Positions	9	3	1	13

Table 4

GENDER REPRESENTATION OF THE DIFFERENT ROLES AT INSTITUTIONS LEVEL

	MALE	FEMALE	NA	TOT
Junior Manager	3			3
Junior Researcher	2	3	1	6
other		1		1
Research/Technology Director	4	2		6
Senior Administrative Staff		3		3
Senior Manager	5	5		10
Senior Researcher	9	5		14
Senior Technical Staff	3	4		7

Table 5

LEADERSHIP POSITIONS IN EMSO ERIC ACTIVITIES

Chart 3: Gender distribution of leadership positions in EMSO ERIC activities

ROLES IN THE INSTITUTIONS

Chart 4: Gender representation of the different roles at institutions level

GENDER DISTRIBUTION EVOLUTION FROM 2017 TO 2021 AT THE EMSO ERIC				
	MALE	FEMALE	NA	TOT
2017	65,9%	34,1%		100%
2021	52%	46%	2%	100%

Table 6

GENDER DISTRIBUTION EVOLUTION FROM 2017 TO 2021 FOR THE LEADERSHIP POSITIONS AT EMSO ERIC				
	MALE	FEMALE	NA	TOT
2017	63%	37%		100%
2021	69%	23%	8%	100%

Table 7

INVOLVEMENT IN EMSO ACTIVITIES: GENERAL TREND

Chart 5: Gender distribution evolution from 2017 to 2021 at the EMSO ERIC.

LEADERSHIP POSITIONS IN EMSO ACTIVITIES

Chart 6: Gender distribution evolution from 2017 to 2021 for the leadership positions at EMSO ERIC

